

High Order Profile Expansion to Tackle the New User Problem on Recommender Systems

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ABSTRACT

Collaborative Filtering algorithms provide users with recommendations based on their opinions, that is, on the ratings given by the user for some items. They are the most popular and widely implemented algorithms in Recommender Systems, especially in e-commerce, considering its good results. However, when the information is extremely sparse, independently of the domain nature, they do not present so good results. In particular, it is difficult to offer recommendations accurate enough to a user who has just arrived to a system or who has rated few items. This is the well-known new user problem, a type of cold-start. Profile Expansion techniques had been already presented as a method to alleviate this situation. These techniques increase the user profile size, by obtaining information about user tastes in distinct ways. This way, recommender algorithms have more information at their disposal, and results get improved. In this paper, we present the High Order Profile Expansion techniques, which combine in different ways the Profile Expansion methods. The results show 110% improvement in precision over the algorithm without Profile Expansion, and 10% improvement over Profile Expansion techniques.

Introduction

The available information is growing every day. Many e-commerce sites have an overwhelming number of items to offer. Because of that, they use Recommender Systems to present suitable information according to user tastes, simplifying the user decision. This way, users are more likely to find what they are looking for and satisfy their information needs, which, at the same time, leads to a potential increase in the sites profits.

Among the recommendation techniques, Collaborative Filtering has shown very good results in many domains. They build profiles based on user tastes. Using these profiles they search for similarities between users and/or items, in order to accomplish different recommendation tasks¹. However, when a particular user has very few ratings, the system is not capable of computing a recommendation good enough for her, since it does not know enough about her tastes². This is the well-known cold start problem and, more concretely, the so-called new user problem.

In this work we explore the Profile Expansion (PE) techniques³, which were proposed to deal with the new user problem without involving the user. They provide automatically the recommender algorithm with more information about user tastes. We analyze their behavior in several situations and we expose their benefits and limitations. Considering this analysis, we propose how to combine these techniques to take advantage of their benefits, while minimizing the impact of their limitations. The new methods obtained are called High Order Profile Expansion (HOPE) techniques and, in fact, could be employed with multiple recommender algorithms.

In the next section we discuss the related work that tackles the new user problem. Especially, we focus on the PE techniques. Following, we explain our proposed method and its variations. Next, we expose the experiments we have performed and we discuss the results. Finally, we present some conclusions and the future work.

State of the Art

Collaborative Filtering techniques are only based on user preferences in the form of item ratings in order to make a recommendation. Among them, the k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) algorithms are very popular⁴ because they are simple, stable, easy to explain⁵ and can make the recommendation on a real-time fashion⁶. They work by finding a set of the k users most similar to the user they are computing a recommendation for (the active user). These users are known as neighbors. The similarity is computed according to a previously defined similarity function. Pearson correlation⁷ or cosine vector similarity⁸ are commonly used.

The kNN algorithms can be classified into user-based and item-based. When a user-based kNN algorithm is employed (similarly with item-based) users rely on the opinion of their k most like-minded people (their neighbors) in order to obtain an

accurate recommendation. Either a rating prediction for a particular item (annotation in context task), or a recommendation list (find good items task), is obtained from the information about these neighbors.

Collaborative Filtering algorithms work well when many ratings are available. However, sometimes the information about a particular user (new user problem), item (new item problem) or, even, the information in the whole system (new system problem) is really scarce. These are the three cold-start situations.

In this work we will focus on the new user problem. In the literature different approaches have been used to address this problem. Basically, they can be divided into those where the user is involved to provide the system with additional information and those without user intervention.

The easiest way to obtain additional information about a user is to ask her directly for it. The process of gathering these initial ratings, known as the elicitation process, can mean the success or the failure in keeping a user in the system⁹. The initial items should be carefully chosen and the number of selected items should not be excessive to avoid bothering the users¹⁰. In exchange, users expect to receive good recommendations. This way, every user will have at least the number of ratings that the system requests while signing up. Different solutions have been proposed to deal with this elicitation process. Rashid *et al.* study how to learn new preferences applying decision theory and entropy¹¹. Other authors use a tree-based bootstrapping process to elicit users to provide their opinions¹², a lazy decision tree, with pair-wise comparisons at the decision nodes¹³ or even gamification¹⁴. As it was previously mentioned, the number of ratings that should be collected from a new user before providing recommendations becomes a key aspect to study¹⁰.

However, sometimes it is not adequate to ask directly the user. For example, these requests may annoy some users who consider not necessary to rate items when they have just arrived to the system. When a user has few ratings the recommendation is usually inaccurate or the system can be incapable of computing the recommendation. In spite of that, depending on the context, it can be even better not to show recommendations, rather than bothering the users. In any case, if the information is scarce but the system can provide a user with recommendations accurate enough to keep her in the system, the elicitation process can be unnecessary.

Other alternatives without user intervention are preferable. For example, in¹⁵ the authors show how recommendations biased by popularity, recency and positive ratings do not suit all new users and explore user coverage to diversify recommendations. Some authors studied how to modify kNN algorithms to improve the recommendations. Traditional similarity measures present several problems when the information is scarce because they are too strict¹⁶. Several similarity measures have been presented as an alternative to the traditional ones in these situations: a new similarity measure for kNN algorithms, based on proximity, impact and popularity of user ratings¹⁷; another one based on the combination of six individual similarity measures¹⁸; or a probability-based similarity measure¹⁹.

In addition to this, PE techniques have been presented as a method to deal with the new user problem without user intervention³. They are based on Query Expansion techniques used in Information Retrieval. In particular, they increase the information available for a user-based kNN algorithm, which accomplishes the find good items task, that is, it tries to find a list of items that can be to the user taste.

Profile Expansion Techniques

In Collaborative Filtering a user profile is comprised of the items that the user has rated, together with the ratings she gave to these items. When a user profile is very small, that is, when there is very scarce information about the user, the similarity measures do not usually work well, so that the neighborhood is not computed correctly. Since the information for computing the recommendation list is obtained from the neighborhood, its accuracy will be low. Therefore, user-based kNN algorithms do not work properly in a new user situation²⁰.

Profile Expansion techniques provide the recommender algorithm with more information about the user. For that, they increase the user profile with additional items, being l the number of items added. Moreover, they do it automatically, without involving the user.

Figure 1 shows the recommendation process when PE is used. First, the initial user profile is expanded by means of an expansion algorithm. The resulting profile is the input for the recommender algorithm, which is in charge of computing the recommendation list. Particularly, as it was already mentioned, a user-based kNN has been used as the main recommender algorithm.

Different approaches have been proposed for expanding the user profile. We focus on collaborative techniques, since they take advantage of the existing user profile and they do not require the user to provide extra information. Among them, item-global (IG) and user-local (UL) techniques showed the best results.

IG techniques expand the user profile searching in the system for the most similar items to those rated by the user. They are applied before computing the neighborhood for the main algorithm. An item-based kNN algorithm is used for that. The recommendation list obtained by means of these techniques has low specificity because global information is used. However, since most items that are similar to those in the user profile are likely to be chosen by the algorithm, these techniques do not

Figure 1. Recommendation process using Profile Expansion.

usually make many mistakes. That is, most items in the recommendation list (not only those that are on top) are frequently related to the user profile items.

On the other hand, UL techniques use only the neighborhood computed for the main algorithm as source of information to find new items. Once these new items are obtained, and, therefore, the expanded profile, the main algorithm computes a new neighborhood in order to present the recommendation list. For the item selection, several techniques were proposed. Most rated (MR) approach selects the most rated items in the neighborhood. Local item neighbors (LN) and user-local clustering (LC) attempt to find similarities between items. Whereas the former only takes into account the items in the neighborhood, LN and LC compute similarities between the neighborhood ratings to the items in the active user profile and the remaining items in the system. With UL algorithms, the most similar items will be probably found, because neighbors will tend to rate them. However, all the items in the neighborhood are not usually related to those in the active user profile. So, the most similar items to those in the user profile will be on the recommendation list, but items unrelated to user tastes can also appear on this list.

When items unrelated to those in the user profile are chosen, PE techniques may induce errors. In this regard, predicted ratings for those items unconnected with user profile items will not usually be accurate enough, since expansion algorithm lacks information to predict their ratings properly. Furthermore, recommender algorithm will also have more difficulties when finding suitable neighbors who share a minimum number of items in common with the active user, because unrelated items tend to appear less frequently in a same user profile than related items. In the next section we present the High Order Profile Expansion techniques, which try to minimize these errors.

High Order Profile Expansion

Every PE technique presented in Section has its own pros and cons. The idea of High Order Profile Expansion is to combine these techniques to take advantage of their benefits and minimize their errors. Using more than one algorithm to expand the user profile, the expansion will be more heterogeneous and, at the same time, still related to the initial user profile. In order to achieve that, we have considered two types of combinations: serial and parallel. For the sake of clarity, we will focus on combinations of two algorithms, although it can be extrapolated to any number of combinations. Also note that the proposed models, although focused on item-global and user-local recommendation algorithms, they could be applied to any user-based kNN algorithm.

Serial

In a serial process the algorithms are used one after the other. That is, there are executed as a pipeline, where the output of the first expansion algorithm is the input of the second one (see Figure 2). The kNN algorithm will use the doubly expanded profile to compute the recommendation list. So, serial combination can be considered as the closest way to the PE original concept, where one algorithm is used for increasing the information available for another algorithm. The first algorithm should work properly and minimize the errors when the information available is very scarce, because an error in this first step is carried along the remaining phases.

Given that we are dealing with an expansion in two steps, there is an alternative where the same algorithm is applied twice. The difference between having a baseline algorithm with a profile expansion size and having the same algorithm executed twice in a serial expansion process with half the size is that items in last positions of the expansion list computed with the baseline algorithm are more likely to be non-relevant and, then, lead to worse recommendations. As profile expansion size increases, the probability of finding non-relevant items at last positions is higher. Therefore, a priori, it will be preferable a serial process with the same algorithm executed twice than the baseline algorithm with a double PE size.

Figure 2. Recommendation process using High Order Profile Expansion with the serial alternative.

Parallel

As it has been already mentioned, PE techniques may induce errors in item selection and rating prediction, which can affect to the final recommendation. This approach attempts to minimize these errors, being the initial user profile the input for all the expansion algorithms used, as it is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Recommendation process using High Order Profile Expansion with the parallel alternative.

Since every expansion algorithm will obtain a new profile and the kNN technique needs a unique profile as input, it is necessary to combine the different profiles. In this combination, we must consider two aspects: rating and item selections. The expanded profiles are obtained independently, so they can present or not items in common. Regarding the item selection, two alternatives have been considered:

- **Union.** The set of items in the final user profile is comprised of the union of the items in every expansion. Therefore, items that appear in only one expanded profile will be also selected. Logically, when combining the same algorithm more than once, the result is the expansion with the biggest PE size, l .
- **Intersection.** The set of items in the final user profile is comprised of the intersection of the items in every expansion. That is, only items appearing in all the expanded profiles will be part of the resulting user profile. In the case of combining the same algorithm more than once, this time the result is the expansion with the smallest l .

As far as rating selection is concerned, when an item appears in more than one expanded profile, the final rating will be the mean of the ratings.

In parallel combination, unlike serial approach, when an error is committed by an expansion algorithm, this error does not affect to the expansion computed by the other algorithm. In exchange, the second algorithm has at its disposal less information, since it only has the initial user profile as input.

Experiments

Experiment Design

The experiments have been performed in a movie recommendation domain. Particularly, we have used a reduced version of the Netflix dataset²¹, where each item matches a movie from the Internet Movie Database (IMDb)¹. This way, we can also do a

¹<http://www.imdb.com>

human evaluation of the results and, in the future, content-based algorithms can also be compared. The final dataset consists of 8,362 items and 478,458 users, who have done 48,715,350 ratings between 1 and 5 inclusive.

Regarding the methodology, we have randomly selected 1000 users for evaluation purposes. The new user problem has been simulated using a Given- N strategy⁸. That is, N ratings have been randomly selected as part of the training subset. The remaining ratings take part of the evaluation subset. We focus on $N = 2$, since it is when the information is more scarce and High Order Profile Expansion techniques can be more useful. Moreover, we study the evolution of the algorithms according to N . From the remaining users, we have randomly chosen 90% of ratings for the training subset.

In relation to the algorithms, we first study how item-global and user-local techniques behave alone, since they are the PE algorithms that obtained the best results in³. Then, we tackle the different ways to combine them. The main algorithm is an user-based kNN algorithm, as it was previously mentioned. The number of neighbors, k , is 25, selected after a cross-validation process.

Since we focus on the find good items task, a list of recommended items is returned by the algorithm. For evaluating the results, we consider 4 as relevance threshold. We have used traditional metrics such as precision and MAP. In particular, Precision-at-5 (P@5), precision at the 5 first positions of the recommendation list, is specially interesting, because it considers those items the user is likely to pay attention to, and not all the list, as MAP does.

Throughout this section only the most significant results will be shown.

Basic Profile Expansion Techniques

Table 1 shows the P@5 results with different l (profile expansion sizes). As discussed in Section , an item-based kNN algorithm is employed for the IG technique. We have used cosine vector similarity for computing the neighborhood. For the IG method, P@5 results improve as l is smaller. However, between $l = 2$ and $l = 5$ there is no significant difference. In fact, MAP results for $l = 5$ are better.

On the other hand, following rows on Table 1 show the P@5 results for the best UL algorithms presented in³: most rated, local item neighbors and user-local clustering. Despite the fact that MR technique only considers the most rated items in the neighborhood and LN and LC techniques try to capture similarities between items, all of them present similar results in P@5. Although it does not present so good results with the MAP metric, MR technique is preferable because of its simplicity. For sake of completeness, last row on Table 1 shows the performance without using Profile Expansion techniques.

Considering these results, PE techniques with $l = 5$ will be used as baselines.

High Order Profile Expansion Alternatives

Among the different HOPE alternatives, we are interested in evaluating which one behaves best and in knowing their pros and cons. In order to achieve that, different experiments have been evaluated. Regarding profile expansion size variations, we have used different l values (2, 5, 10 and 15) to check how the l combinations affect the results. Moreover, it is also interesting to know how the distinct algorithms evolve according to N , that is, according to the amount of information available.

Serial

In serial combinations, two Profile Expansion techniques are used, one after the other. Although algorithms in Section obtain their best results with $l = 5$, the best results combining these algorithms in a serial process are obtained with $l = 2$. In fact, the PE algorithms also present very good results with this profile expansion size.

Table 2 shows P@5 and MAP results for $l = 2$ combinations. Results for l values of 5, 10 and 15 are omitted due to their lower performance.

Unlike parallel alternatives, in this case the execution order may be important. So, first, we will focus on algorithms order. Regarding the results, LN algorithm works better when it is used as the first algorithm. Moreover, IG algorithm performs better when it is the second algorithm, improving the MAP values with respect to the baselines. MR and LC algorithms depend on which algorithm is combined with them. These observations are predictable and logical, because when the information about a user is scarce, global information is more prone to errors, since it is more difficult to select which items are really similar to those in the user profile. However, when working with local information, although there is less information available, it tends to be related to the user profile. From now on, when two algorithms can be combined using two different orders, we will only present the order that performs better.

In order to deal with the different combinations, we will divide them into three groups: first, those that combine IG with any other algorithm; second, those that combine two different UL algorithms; and, third, those that combine an algorithm with itself.

Figure 4 shows P@5 and MAP results when user-local techniques are combined with the IG technique. When $N = 2$, that is, when the available information about the active user is extremely scarce, this kind of combinations improves the precision baselines. In particular, combining the MR algorithm with the IG algorithm improves almost 10% the results. Moreover, MAP results regarding MR gets better too. Since they use different types of information, using both the recommendation list can be

Table 1. P@5 and MAP for Profile Expansion baseline algorithms. Best values are highlighted.

Algorithms	l	$N = 2$		$N = 10$	
		P@5	MAP	P@5	MAP
IG	2	0.125	0.029	0.123	0.040
	5	0.122	0.035	0.118	0.045
	10	0.100	0.038	0.097	0.046
	15	0.086	0.039	0.076	0.044
	20	0.078	0.038	0.071	0.043
	50	0.044	0.034	0.048	0.037
LC	2	0.136	0.025	0.148	0.035
	5	0.140	0.030	0.140	0.036
	10	0.123	0.034	0.128	0.040
	15	0.112	0.036	0.118	0.041
	20	0.102	0.038	0.110	0.042
	50	0.077	0.040	0.085	0.039
LN	2	0.134	0.023	0.140	0.037
	5	0.139	0.029	0.141	0.039
	10	0.128	0.032	0.140	0.038
	15	0.121	0.035	0.141	0.037
	20	0.111	0.037	0.138	0.037
	50	0.083	0.041	0.137	0.037
MR	2	0.138	0.024	0.146	0.031
	5	0.147	0.029	0.139	0.035
	10	0.134	0.032	0.127	0.038
	15	0.117	0.033	0.123	0.037
	20	0.109	0.036	0.115	0.038
	50	0.076	0.040	0.087	0.042
No PE	-	0.078	0.029	0.140	0.036

Table 2. P@5 and MAP for High Order Profile Expansion serial combinations, with $l = 2$. Best values are highlighted.

Algorithms		$N = 2$		$N = 10$	
1	2	P@5	MAP	P@5	MAP
LC	LC	0.153	0.026	0.146	0.034
	LN	0.147	0.026	0.148	0.036
	MR	0.156	0.025	0.153	0.036
	IG	0.149	0.032	0.147	0.040
LN	LC	0.154	0.027	0.151	0.035
	LN	0.142	0.024	0.140	0.037
	MR	0.158	0.025	0.151	0.033
	IG	0.156	0.032	0.127	0.041
MR	LC	0.163	0.026	0.153	0.034
	LN	0.152	0.025	0.146	0.032
	MR	0.155	0.024	0.151	0.034
	IG	0.160	0.030	0.137	0.039
IG	LC	0.139	0.030	0.144	0.040
	LN	0.137	0.031	0.128	0.041
	MR	0.145	0.029	0.143	0.041
	IG	0.133	0.035	0.129	0.045
No PE		0.078	0.029	0.140	0.036

Figure 4. Evolution according to N, High Order Profile Expansion using serial combinations with IG technique and $l = 2$.

more accurate, because more information about the user is achieved. In addition to this, and due to the same reason, if LN is the algorithm that is combined, then the improvement in P@5 is important with respect to the LN and IG algorithms, when N is low.

The behavior of MR algorithm and LN algorithm with IG approach is very similar. The precision tends to diminish according to the increase of N . This is because the scarcity of information is not so critical when $N = 10$. In fact, whereas the algorithm without PE can obtain a precision about 0.14, High Order alternatives can induce several errors in rating prediction, which can lead to lose accuracy in the recommendation.

Regarding the serial combination of UL algorithms, they also present good results, as it can be seen in Figure 5. Again, it is with $N = 2$ when we obtain the greatest improvement, increasing the usefulness of PE techniques when very little information

about the user is available. Given that MR algorithm had originally high precision, the combinations with this algorithm reach high precisions too. In this case, good results are also achieved when $N = 10$. However, MAP values obtained are worse than those reached when IG techniques participate in the combinations. IG techniques employ global information, so most items used for expansion will be close to user tastes, whereas using UL techniques can imply that some items not so similar to user tastes are incorporated to the user profile. Anyway, as it was mentioned in Section , in general, we consider more valuable P@5 than MAP for the find good items task, although it depends on the particular context of each system.

Figure 5. Evolution according to N, High Order Profile Expansion using serial combinations with UL techniques and $l = 2$.

Finally, an algorithm can also be combined with itself. The results are shown in Figure 6. All the algorithms, but LN algorithm, improve the precision results when they are executed in a serial process. These results confirm that it is preferable a serial process than the baseline algorithm with double the profile expansion size, as it was mentioned in Section . MAP results are only slightly lower than those obtained with the baseline algorithms.

Figure 6. Evolution according to N, High Order Profile Expansion using the same algorithm twice and $l = 2$.

As a general result, the serial combinations of UL algorithms show very good results in P@5, whereas the combinations with IG techniques present better results in MAP. Mixing MR algorithm with either LC or IG techniques is particularly interesting, since these combinations have a 10% improvement in P@5 over UL algorithms results and around 110% improvement over the algorithm without PE. In fact, the combination of MR approach with any other alternative always improves the baselines results. The reason is that they complement each other, since they use different sources of information.

Table 3. P@5 and MAP for High Order Profile Expansion parallel alternatives. Intersection alternative with $l = 5$ for all the algorithms but IG, with $l = 100$. Union alternative with $l = 2$ for all the algorithms. Best values are highlighted.

Algorithms		Intersection				Union			
1	2	$N = 2$		$N = 10$		$N = 2$		$N = 10$	
		P@5	MAP	P@5	MAP	P@5	MAP	P@5	MAP
	LC	0.128	0.029	0.148	0.038	0.142	0.031	0.140	0.041
IG	LN	0.139	0.028	0.141	0.039	0.134	0.030	0.125	0.040
	MR	0.133	0.027	0.143	0.038	0.144	0.030	0.148	0.040
LC	LN	0.146	0.029	0.141	0.038	0.137	0.025	0.147	0.034
	MR	0.143	0.029	0.152	0.036	0.144	0.027	0.152	0.034
LN	MR	0.147	0.028	0.141	0.038	0.138	0.024	0.148	0.032

Parallel

The parallel variants presented in this paper are union and intersection. Table 3 shows P@5 and MAP results for both alternatives. Note that as union and intersection operations are commutative, only one combination is presented for each pair of algorithms.

Intersection alternative consists in intersecting expanded profiles obtained with different techniques in order to create a unique expanded profile. These techniques can be of different nature. Because of that, their expanded profiles may have no items in common if we take into account very few items as expansion. This could cause that the Profile Expansion step to become useless. Therefore, for this variant profile expansion sizes have been increased with respect to the serial alternative, so that it is more probable that two different techniques have items in common.

While $l = 5$ is enough for obtaining good results when only UL algorithms are considered, it does not happen the same when IG techniques are used. In fact, in the whole dataset there can be many items similar to those in the user profile and only a few of these are likely to appear as items rated by user neighbors. This is the reason why we decided to use a bigger profile expansion size for IG algorithm ($l = 100$). Indeed, our results confirmed this assumption.

From Table 3, we can observe that MAP values are quite good, but P@5 results for the parallel variation do not improve those obtained with the serial alternative.

On the other hand, union variation puts together the expansions obtained with the different algorithms. We have employed $l = 2$ as profile expansion size. As shown in Table 3 the results do not improve those obtained with the serial alternative either. In fact, no combination gets a P@5 value better than MR baseline algorithm.

So, despite the fact that with the parallel alternatives the second expansion algorithm is not affected by the errors committed by the first one, the serial results are better because the second algorithm is provided with more information.

Conclusions and Future Work

In this work, we study High Order Profile Expansion techniques in depth, which deal with the new user problem in Collaborative Filtering. In particular, we propose two methods to combine them so that we can take advantage of their benefits and mitigate their errors. These alternatives are called serial and parallel.

The experiments have shown how the serial alternative performs better than the parallel one. The reason is that in the serial alternative an algorithm is supplied with the information obtained by another algorithm. Without it, the second algorithm may not obtain this information. That does not happen with the parallel alternative, where the algorithms use the same information.

Regarding the different serial combinations, those where MR algorithm takes part obtain the best P@5 results. Moreover, IG algorithm increases MAP obtained with UL algorithms when they are used together. This way, the combination of IG and MR methods performs very well, mainly when N is low.

Furthermore, when two different UL methods are combined, the results in P@5 reach 0.145 with all the values studied for N . However, MAP values do not surpass those obtained by MR method, the lowest among all the UL alternatives.

Another way to combine PE techniques is to execute the same algorithm two consecutive times. In this case, all the algorithms, but LN method, improve the results obtained when they are executed only once.

In the future, we plan to evaluate how a content-based algorithm behaves in combination with other PE algorithms, since, throughout this paper, only item-based kNN algorithm has been used as IG method. Other Collaborative Filtering algorithms apart from neighbor-based ones could also be used and tested. In fact, we plan to combine more than two different algorithms,

since in this work we have analyzed the two by two combinations. Finally, we are also interested in analyzing how these techniques behave in a new system situation.

References

1. Herlocker, J. L., Konstan, J. A., Terveen, L. G. & Riedl, J. T. Evaluating collaborative filtering recommender systems. *ACM Trans. Inf. Syst.* **22**, 5–53, DOI: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/963770.963772> (2004).
2. Sarumathi, M. *et al.* Systematic approach for cold start issues in recommendations system. In *2016 International Conference on Recent Trends in Information Technology (ICRTIT)*, 1–7 (IEEE, 2016).
3. Formoso, V., Fernández, D., Cacheda, F. & Carneiro, V. Using profile expansion techniques to alleviate the new user problem. *Inf. Process. Manag.* **49**, 659–672, DOI: [10.1016/j.ipm.2012.07.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2012.07.005) (2013).
4. Herlocker, J., Konstan, J. A. & Riedl, J. An empirical analysis of design choices in neighborhood-based collaborative filtering algorithms. *Inf. Retr.* **5**, 287–310, DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1023/A:1020443909834> (2002).
5. Desrosiers, C. & Karypis, G. A comprehensive survey of neighborhood-based recommendation methods. In Ricci, F., Rokach, L., Shapira, B. & Kantor, P. B. (eds.) *Recommender Systems Handbook*, 107–144 (Springer, 2011).
6. Jalili, M., Ahmadian, S., Izadi, M., Moradi, P. & Salehi, M. Evaluating collaborative filtering recommender algorithms: A survey. *IEEE Access* **6**, 74003–74024 (2018).
7. Resnick, P., Iacovou, N., Suchak, M., Bergstrom, P. & Riedl, J. GroupLens: an open architecture for collaborative filtering of netnews. In *Proceedings of the 1994 ACM conference on Computer supported cooperative work, CSCW '94*, 175–186, DOI: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/192844.192905> (ACM, New York, NY, USA, 1994).
8. Breese, J. S., Heckerman, D. & Kadie, C. Empirical analysis of predictive algorithms for collaborative filtering. In *Proceedings of the Fourteenth conference on Uncertainty in artificial intelligence, UAI'98*, 43–52 (Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc., San Francisco, CA, USA, 1998).
9. Elahi, M., Reppas, V. & Ricci, F. Rating Elicitation Strategies for Collaborative Filtering E-Commerce and Web Technologies. vol. 85 of *Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing*, chap. 14, 160–171, DOI: [10.1007/978-3-642-23014-1_14](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-23014-1_14) (Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2011).
10. Cremonesi, P., Garzotto, F. & Turrin, R. User effort vs. accuracy in rating-based elicitation. In *Proceedings of the sixth ACM conference on Recommender systems, RecSys '12*, 27–34, DOI: [10.1145/2365952.2365963](https://doi.org/10.1145/2365952.2365963) (ACM, New York, NY, USA, 2012).
11. Rashid, A. M., Karypis, G. & Riedl, J. Learning preferences of new users in recommender systems: an information theoretic approach. *SIGKDD Explor. Newsl.* **10**, 90–100, DOI: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1540276.1540302> (2008).
12. Golbandi, N., Koren, Y. & Lempel, R. Adaptive bootstrapping of recommender systems using decision trees. In *Proceedings of the fourth ACM international conference on Web search and data mining, WSDM '11*, 595–604, DOI: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1935826.1935910> (ACM, New York, NY, USA, 2011).
13. Rokach, L. & Kisilevich, S. Initial profile generation in recommender systems using pairwise comparison. *IEEE Transactions on Syst. Man, Cybern. Part C* **42**, 1854–1859, DOI: [10.1109/TSMCC.2012.2197679](https://doi.org/10.1109/TSMCC.2012.2197679) (2012).
14. Feil, S., Kretzer, M., Werder, K. & Maedche, A. Using gamification to tackle the cold-start problem in recommender systems. In *Proceedings of the 19th ACM Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work and Social Computing Companion, 253–256* (ACM, 2016).
15. Silva, N., Carvalho, D., Pereira, A. C., Mourão, F. & Rocha, L. The pure cold-start problem: A deep study about how to conquer first-time users in recommendations domains. *Inf. Syst.* **80**, 1 – 12, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.is.2018.09.001> (2019).
16. Cacheda, F., Carneiro, V., Fernández, D. & Formoso, V. Improving k-nearest neighbors algorithms: practical application of dataset analysis. In *Proceedings of the 20th ACM international conference on Information and knowledge management, CIKM '11*, 2253–2256, DOI: [10.1145/2063576.2063939](https://doi.org/10.1145/2063576.2063939) (ACM, New York, NY, USA, 2011).
17. Ahn, H. J. A new similarity measure for collaborative filtering to alleviate the new user cold-starting problem. *Inf. Sci.* **178**, 37–51, DOI: [10.1016/j.ins.2007.07.024](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2007.07.024) (2008).
18. Bobadilla, J., Ortega, F., Hernando, A. & Bernal, J. A collaborative filtering approach to mitigate the new user cold start problem. *Know.-Based Syst.* **26**, 225–238, DOI: [10.1016/j.knosys.2011.07.021](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2011.07.021) (2012).

19. Piccart, B., Struyf, J. & Blockeel, H. Alleviating the sparsity problem in collaborative filtering by using an adapted distance and a graph-based method. In *SIAM International Conference on Data Mining*, SDM 2010, 189–198 (2010).
20. Cacheda, F., Carneiro, V., Fernández, D. & Formoso, V. Comparison of collaborative filtering algorithms: Limitations of current techniques and proposals for scalable, high-performance recommender systems. *ACM Trans. Web* **5**, 2:1–2:33, DOI: <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1921591.1921593> (2011).
21. Bennett, J. & Lanning, S. The netflix prize. In *Proceedings of KDD Cup and Workshop*, KDDCup '07, 3–6 (ACM, San Jose, California, USA, 2007).

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Author contributions statement

D.F. and V.C. prepared the state-of-the-art analysis, V.F. developed the proposed High Order Profile Expansion model, D.F., V.F. and F.C. designed and conducted the experiments and F.C. and V.C. analysed the results. All authors reviewed the article.